

A Remote Visual Interface Tool for Simulation Control And Display

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Abstract

Visual Interactive Simulation (VIS) is an animation method used to create a dynamic display of a system model, and to allow the viewer to control and interact with the running simulation. This paper discusses the design and development of the Visual Interactive Simulation Interface Tool (VISIT). VISIT was designed to provide the graphical representation and user interface for a simulation that is running on another processor utilizing internet communications. Since the simulation processor may be any system capable of implementing the proper network protocol, specialized processors with no graphics display devices can benefit from this architecture.

The system provides support for various input devices to control the simulation display and environment. Simulation objects are displayed using either a three-dimensional wireframe representation or a Gouraud shaded representation. Viewer interaction to the simulation is provided by a collection of commands that allow the viewer to initialize, start, stop, abort, and restart the simulation. The viewer also has the ability to establish checkpoints. Upon reaching a checkpoint the viewer can step through the output display and/or manipulate the objects within the simulation.

1 Introduction

A visual interactive simulation as defined by O'Keefe is "a simulation which produces a dynamic display of the system model, and allows the user to interact with the running simulation" [10:461]. VISIT provides the capability to graphically display the output from a simulation running on another processor. The simulation processor is accessible via network communications to the graphics display workstation. The viewer is allowed to manipulate and control the simulation through a collection of commands.

The methodology developed is of particular interest because of its ability to interface to a wide range of simulations. It also provides the freedom of allowing the simulation processor to be any system capable of implementing the Transmission Control Protocol/ Internet Protocol (TCP/IP).

1.1 Background

According to Biles a simulation is defined as "the development of a mathematical-logic model of a system and the experimental manipulation of the model on a digital computer" [2:7]. For a model to be useful, it is imperative that all its relevant behavior and characteristics be determined in a feasible way. It may be determined numerically, analytically, or by running the model and providing to it input, and observing the results; the latter being a simulation. Although simulations provide a powerful tool for analyzing a given model, they are typically very large, application specific, and difficult to use.

Existing simulations are often very large, having been built over time by numerous programmers, and produce large amounts of paper output. There is either limited or no feedback presented to the viewer to identify how far the simulation has progressed. The simulations generally use limited graphics capability or none at all. They are developed for specific applications; any graphical representation incorporated into the simulation may require considerable redevelopment effort when the simulation is modified.

The Air Force Institute of Technology (AFIT) needed an interactive visual interface to enhance and supplement its in-house simulation capabilities. AFIT has numerous computer systems that are capable of running large-scale simulations, but did not have a generic interface to display the running simulation graphically. Also, there is no capability to allow the user to interact with the running simulation.

1.2 Other Research Efforts

Simple animation to represent a discrete-event simulation has existed for many years. Amiry used animation in his simulation of a steel melting shop in 1965, but the present approach to VIS was developed by Hurriion [8] in 1976 at the University of Warwick, England. Hurriion was constructing simulations for job shop scheduling applications in manufacturing.

Hurriion's initial applications represent interaction in which the model prompts the user for a decision or additional data. Additional research at the University of Warwick created user-prompted interaction. User-prompted

interaction allows the user to suspend the running simulation and thus control the interaction.

Other research and commercial development followed as the capabilities of VIS became known. Crookes [4] discussed the value of VIS for developers when they verify and validate a model. Interaction and animation provide instant feedback to the user and a mechanism to determine the validity of the model. By altering various parameters a user could observe the effects and compare them to what was expected.

Bell states that there are four major issues in VIS which require further research. These issues are the type and quantity of the virtual display, software and hardware for VIS, the need for methodology, and the role of expert systems [1:114]. The importance of good screen layout is known to developers, but few developers have been trained in interactive computer graphics design. Present systems require the development of a simulation model first, then incorporate the graphical interface and interaction. VIS has typically been developed on stand-alone IBM-AT class computers with limited graphics capability [1:110].

Animation is one way of providing a visual representation for the human-computer interface of a software system. A human's perceptual capabilities are optimized for real-time image processing. Interactive graphics can communicate instantly data in multidimensions concerning the internal state of a dynamic process. A fully interactive animation must interpret user input in relation to screen images, in addition to creating the images in the first place [6:300]. The field of human-computer interaction combines many disciplines: computer graphics, human factors, cognitive psychology, and artificial intelligence.

1.3 Objectives

The goal of this research was to develop a generic interface on a general-purpose graphics workstation which would allow a viewer to represent, control, and manipulate a concurrently executing discrete-event simulation. The simulation processor is accessible to the graphics display workstation via network communications.

To be useful, the remote visual interface must be able to:

- Support a wide range of simulations
- Allow a viewer to control and interact with the simulation
- Display realistic animation

2 System Design

The emphasis of the design of the visual interface system was to provide a user-friendly generic interface. The design of the Visual Interactive Simulation Interface Tool decomposes into three major components:

1. Generic Interface

2. Data Representation

3. Communications

This interface was developed to run on a Silicon Graphics Iris 4D workstation and supports data communications that utilize the application layer TCP/IP protocol package. All communication between the simulation and the graphics display system will take place on an ethernet LAN.

The viewer is allowed to interactively suspend the display of the simulation. When the display is suspended, the viewer is allowed to move objects within the display, delete objects, or select objects to use as a viewpoint reference. The viewer is allowed to interact with any object known to the graphics display system and displayable from the current viewpoint. The viewpoint may be changed during the suspension.

The viewer is allowed to establish checkpoints during execution. Checkpoints are specific times during the course of the simulation at which all relevant data are stored. Upon reaching a checkpoint, the viewer is allowed to manipulate the simulation, return to a previous simulation checkpoint, step forward through the display, continue the simulation, or restart the simulation.

The interface supports interaction devices other than a mouse and keyboard. The ability to pick an object in a 3-dimensional display requires a 3-dimensional picking device.

The interface supports simulations that have static and movable objects. Static objects are objects that never move or change, such as the terrain/playing surface. Movable objects are those that will change position during the simulation. All objects known by the graphics display system are viewable.

The system supports the ability to link each object within the simulation to an icon representation for the display. It also supports a smooth movement of objects, based on position and orientation, that is proportional to simulation time.

3 Implementation

The overall strategy used in developing the implementation of the VISIT was one of prototyping. The project was broken down into three main areas during the design phase; data representation/processing, communications, and graphical display/user interaction issues. To handle this project in an orderly manner, a prototype for each major area was implemented and tested before they were integrated into a complete system.

The graphical display system used for the development of this software interface was a Silicon Graphics Iris 4D/85GT. The simulation processor used for the development of this effort was a Sun4/260 workstation.

3.1 Generic Interface

The interface between the simulation processor and the graphics display system had to be generic enough to sup-

port a wide range of simulations. The interface had to support the display of existing simulations without forcing a major rewrite of the simulation software. To support this requirement, two modes of operation were designed, *datamode* and *simmode*.

Datamode Datamode allows the graphical display system to display the results of an existing simulation by executing a software tool on the simulation processor. This software tool reads a datafile that contains converted simulation output. The contents of the datafile are sent to the graphical display system over the LAN using a prescribed message packet format. In this mode the simulation does not have to be altered if the required information for the datafile is available in the current simulation output. The simulation output must be converted into the datafile format externally. The basic algorithm is as follows:

1. Initialize the network socket
2. Establish a handshake with the graphics display system
3. Open the datafile
4. While not end of file:
 - (a) Check for incoming network messages
 - (b) Read a record from the file
 - (c) Create the network message packet
 - (d) Send the message packet

Once the datafile is completely sent across the network, the system continually checks the network socket for incoming messages from the graphics display system.

Simmode In this mode of operation the simulation is executing concurrently on the simulation processor as the graphics display system displays the output. The output, using the network message packet format, is provided to the graphics display system via the LAN that interconnects the two systems.

This mode of operation provides more capability to the viewer but has the restriction that the graphical display system can only display the information at the rate at which it receives packets from the simulation processor.

The basic algorithm is as follows:

1. Initialize the network socket
2. Establish a handshake with the graphics display system
3. Begin the simulation
4. Until the simulation ends:
 - (a) Check for incoming network messages
 - (b) Process an event
 - (c) Create the network message packet
 - (d) Send the message packet

In *simmode* the simulation processor will create the network message packets as it executes the simulation. The processor will have to perform some initialization tasks before beginning the execution of the simulation.

User Interaction In order to allow the viewer to interact with the simulation, a picking device had to be incorporated into the system. However, it is very difficult for a viewer to select an object from a three-dimensional display using a two-dimensional device; therefore an external three-dimensional device was utilized.

The CIS Dimension Six spaceball was chosen for its unique capabilities. The spaceball provides both the direction of movement and the amount of movement. This provides a fast and controlled movement of the cursor on the display screen along any of the three primary axes in either a positive or negative direction. In addition, the device provides the capability to provide three degrees of rotation in either a positive or negative direction. Selecting objects within the current display will require the viewer to manipulate a cursor over the object desired. Once positioned, pressing a button or key indicates to the interface select the object nearest the cursor.

When the spaceball functions are required, the viewer presses the applicable keyboard key and the system will execute the code that accesses the device for data. When using the spaceball, the display is usually paused, and no concern exists for how fast the frame buffer is updated because the simulation objects are suspended at their current location. Once the viewer has finished using the spaceball, the viewer can toggle off access to the spaceball before releasing the display in motion.

This external device requires cpu processing time for the system to read from the device and write to the device. To maintain a sufficient display rate on the graphics display system, this input and output had to function at a rate that would minimize the delay encountered using external I/O devices. An existing Virtual Environment Display System (VEDS) was available that provided the ability to offload this requirement to a separate processor [7].

The Virtual Environment Display System [7] is a system of software libraries and various hardware devices that support virtual environments such as VISIT. VEDS provides a means of allowing a separate computer system to handle the interaction with certain external I/O devices. The VEDS processor establishes a communication link to the device, continually reads data from the device, and stores the latest data from the device into memory. This memory is shared with another process running on the VEDS processor, which in turn establishes a network connection to the graphics display system.

Viewer Control Throughout the execution of the simulation the viewer maintains considerable control over the viewer's display. Once the display has been set in motion, the viewer may pause the display, reset the simulation clock, step through the display a frame at a time, or establish a checkpoint. Viewer control is maintained

by storing and keeping all update records for each object within memory. Resetting the display clock time is accomplished by relocating the current location pointer for each object within the data structure of location records.

The simulation clock may be reset to time 0 or to any time up to the current simulation clock time. A checkpoint can be set any time during the display of a simulation for any simulation time into the future. Upon reaching this time, the display will pause and allow the viewer to interact with the simulation objects. Once the viewer has finished interacting with the simulation the display may be set back in motion with a single keystroke.

The viewer has complete control over what position to use as a viewing position of the simulation. The viewer may establish a viewpoint at a static location and watch the entire scenario from that position. However, the interface allows both keyboard control and spaceball control to maneuver the viewing position. This enables the viewer to position the viewpoint virtually anywhere that is within the hardware limits of the display system.

Another useful feature is one that allows the viewer to position the viewpoint within one of the simulation objects. This provides the viewer with the ability to watch the simulation from that object's moving perspective. This view ranges from the slow ground-level perspective of a tank to the view obtained from a missile launched from an aircraft.

3.2 Data Representations

Simulation Objects The graphical display system and the simulation processor must have a common reference to the various objects within the simulation. To ensure that both systems uniquely identify all objects correctly, initialization records are sent by the simulation processor to identify each object. The initialization links each object with a geometric description file for that object. The file contains the polygonal description which is used by the graphical display system [5].

The task of maintaining the location, orientation, and characteristics of all objects within the simulation requires a detailed data structure that can be easily manipulated and maintained. The various characteristics of an object are established when the object is linked to an icon index. As update records are received from the simulation processor the data structure is updated. During each frame update the current position of each object is updated and stored in the position field of the structure.

VISIT uses an extrapolation method to update an object's position and orientation during the display process. Given a known position, orientation, velocity, and time, an object's future position can be determined. This assumes a straight line movement and/or a constant rotation. During each frame update the system performs the following steps to update each object.

1. Check to see if an object is activated at this time
2. Check for a new update record
3. Check to see if object should be terminated

4. Update position

In this mode of operation an object can be displayed as soon as it becomes "active" in the simulation. The graphics display system utilizes the velocity information and the frame update rate to determine the next location to display each object. Whenever a new location becomes current (based on simulation time) the velocity data from the new record is used.

Network Message Packets The graphical display system and the simulation processor will require an enormous amount of internetwork traffic. The amount of traffic is dependent upon the size of the simulation being displayed. A very large simulation containing hundreds, perhaps thousands of objects, will communicate one message packet for each update to each object. These packets are read by the graphics display system one at a time within the display loop. Small simulations, on the other hand, may communicate fewer message packets, and thus create less network traffic.

A message packet format was adapted from an existing internet communications package. The message packet header contains a field which identifies the type of information contained in the packet body. Certain record types contain zero bytes of data in the body while others contain over 500 bytes of data. Since the interface reads the message header first to determine the record type and length of the message body, time is saved by reading the exact number of bytes in the body instead of having a default size large enough to contain any message body.

Terrain Realistic terrain features were desired in the display of certain simulations. Flat terrain, although easy to generate and display, provides little realistic qualities to the displayed image. A three-dimensional description was desired in a format that was fairly simple to incorporate into the graphics display system as well as the simulation processor. The terrain description was generated using the same geometric description format as the simulation objects [5].

3.3 Communications

The discussion in this section is concerned mainly with the communications between the workstation running the *display system* and the remote simulation processor.

In order to support a wide range of simulations the graphics display system must communicate with a wide range of computer systems. The communications protocol had to be generic, reliable, and available. The Transmission Control Protocol / Internet Protocol (TCP/IP) satisfied these requirements. TCP/IP is a common term referring to the Defense Advanced Research Project Agency Internet network protocols developed for use on the ARPANET. TCP and IP are only two of the many protocols that were developed. The internet protocols support heterogeneous host systems and architectures that utilize a wide variety of internal data structures [3].

The Internet Protocol is the lowest-level protocol and provides the network-level services of host-addressing, routing, and packet disassemble and reassemble. All other protocols use the services of the IP. TCP provides reliable and controlled transmission of data from the application to the IP [9:344]. A more detailed discussion can be found in [9].

TCP/IP provides the generic network communications between the simulation processor and the graphics display system in a reliable manner. The simulation processor sends data records and status records to the graphics display system and the display system sends command records and status records to the simulation processor. In order to maintain efficient processing, the graphics display system performs "nonwait" reads from the network socket. The system queries the network socket to see if any messages are pending; if none are available it continues on instead of waiting.

The ordering of messages received from the simulation processor is critical to the graphics display system. The icon description record used to link the simulation object type to a geometric description file must be received first.

Once all objects types that will be used by the simulation are known to the graphics display system, the object records can begin. When a new object is created in the simulation, an icon assignment record must be received. This record links the simulation object to an icon file that will be used to represent the object on the display screen. After the object is linked to an icon, the initial position record must be received. This record identifies the location, orientation, velocity, and simulation time at which the object will be at that location.

The graphics display system will wait to begin the display of the simulation until a special message packet, used to instruct the display system to begin the display process, is received. The simulation should send this message after all known objects that have a location at time 0 are sent to the graphics display system. Once the display system receives this record it will begin to display and update all objects known to the graphics display system. New objects can be created after the start of the display process.

The graphics display system sends network packets to the simulation processor when the viewer stops the simulation to manipulate a known object. When the viewer relocates or removes an object from the display system, this information is passed to the simulation processor. The simulation must then respond to those records and reply with object update records.

4 Results

Fast, efficient network communications are maintained between the simulation processor and the graphics display system. Realistic animation is achieved in most situations, but is highly dependent upon the complexity of the scene. The viewer maintains complete control over the execution and display of the simulation. Existing simula-

tion output, once converted into a format-specific datafile, can be displayed utilizing an incorporated software tool that executes on the simulation processor.

4.1 Performance

A test scenario was constructed that contained 35 simulation objects. The objects ranged from missiles that utilize 25 polygons in their description to aircraft that contain over 100 polygons in their description. The scenario had an average of 2,000 polygons within each frame. There were 645 location records transferred from the simulation processor to the graphics display system. The vast majority of these records were for four aircraft that were in existence throughout the entire simulation.

Several factors were critical in determining the frame update rate. The terrain was a simple 3-dimensional description using 1,152 3-sided polygons. A grid was formed by creating closed-line polygons using the same description as the terrain. Combined with the simulation objects a frame contained 3,150 polygons on average when the terrain features and grid were displayed. Another key factor was the display of the clock statistics. This entailed displaying raster font character strings on the screen and querying the system clock during the display loop.

When the entire window contains terrain features there is little performance degregation displaying the grid and clock statistics. This is due in part to the system having to paint each pixel in the frame buffer each time through the display loop. When the terrain features are not displayed, the frame update rate is almost tripled, but a big degregation is seen when the clock statistics are displayed. The final factor was the spaceball access time, which was discussed previously in Section 3.1. There is little performance loss when the terrain occupies the entire window and the spaceball is being accessed in server mode. However, in local mode the spaceball reduces the frame update rate severely.

4.2 Conclusions

The viewer has the ability with this interface to completely control a simulation's execution and display. This provides the necessary capabilities so often needed by developers and users. The interface has the ability to see the simulation as it executes knowing immediately if the simulation is valid, knowing immediately if the input data was in the correct format, knowing immediately if results were obtained.

It has the ability for a developer to validate the requirements with a user by showing instead of explaining. It contains the ability for a group to see the execution and control of a simulation, which may or may not be executing in the local environment. Finally, the interface has the ability to display a simulation that executes on hardware with no graphics display capability.

5 Summary

The execution of a concurrent simulation can be represented graphically, controlled interactively, and manipulated dynamically. The representation is accomplished using AFIT standard polygonal descriptions to represent the simulation objects in either a wireframe or Gouraud shaded display. The simulation is controlled by allowing the viewer to stop, start, restart, suspend, and abort the simulation. The manipulation is controlled dynamically through a standard, parameterized interface on a general purpose graphics workstation utilizing network communications.

The simulation interface functions much the same as an interactive symbolic debugger. The viewer is allowed to maneuver an object, remove an object, set checkpoints, and step through an execution. The checkpoints allow the viewer to "retreat" back to this position after following some path that proved undesirable.

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